

A STUDY OF CHROMATIC NUMBERS IN FRACTAL GRAPHS AND THEIR APPLICATIONS IN VARIOUS FIELDS

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ABSTRACT: In Mathematics, one of the significant areas is graphs. A graph is a mathematical diagram used to show the relations between objects and some quantity. The graph is a mathematical representation of a network and it describes the relationship among a finite number of points connected by lines. The theory of graphs can be applied to various problems. This paper analyses the chromatic number of various graphs Null Graph, Trivial Graph, Complete Graph, Star Graph, Wheel Graph, Cyclic graph, and a brief discussion about the fractal graphs and their applications.

Keywords: Graph, Colouring of graphs, Fractal graph, Chromatic Number

INTRODUCTION: Graph Theory is used in vast areas of science and technology. Graphs are used to define the flow of computation, to represent networks of communication, and data organization, to ensure transaction-safe, persistent storing and querying of graph-structured data, finding the shortest path in the network, the shortest path between two nodes in Google Maps. Unique of the important topics in graphs is graph coloring [1]. Graph coloring has many considerable applications, such as map coloring, scheduling problems, school timetables, etc. Several interesting practical problems can be modeled by graph coloring. In this paper, we discuss the application of graph coloring to different problem situations.

Keywords: Graph, Coloring of graphs, Vertex degrees, scheduling, coloring

GRAPH COLORING: Graph coloring is the colors to each vertex of a graph G such that no adjacent vertices should have same colors.

CHROMATIC NUMBER: The minimum number of colors [2] required to color the non-adjacent vertices of the graph is called the chromatic number [3].

NULL GRAPH: The empty graph or null graph may also be the graph with no vertices and no edges.

Figure-1

Therefore Chromatic Number(G) = Number of Vertices $V(G)$

TRIVIAL GRAPH: A graph is said to be trivial if a finite graph contains only one vertex and no edge. It has colored by only one color only i.e. Chromatic Number(G) = 1

COMPLETE GRAPH: A complete graph is a graph that has every single vertex that should have edges with other vertices present in the graph. Therefore Chromatic Number(G) = 5.

STAR GRAPH: Star graph contains n vertices in that $n-1$ vertices have degree 1 and single vertex should have degree $n-1$.

WHEEL GRAPH: A wheel graph W_n contains an additional vertex to the cycle, W_n for, and connects this new vertex to each of the vertices in C_n , by new edges.

CYCLIC GRAPH: If every vertex of a graph G is of degree 2, then G is said to be a Cyclic graph, and denoted by C_n .

FRACTAL GRAPH

A fractal is a different geometric shape that has the same measurements of non-sameness on all scales. Fractals can be supposed of as never-finish patterns. Fractals are the kind of shapes we see in nature of designs. We find mountains, rocks, trees, and cloud formations in nature, but what is the geometrical shape for a mountain shape? We can see the top position of the Cauliflower. How can we determine the shape of a flood ice cream in the cup? Science continues to discover an incredibly reliable order behind the universe's most seemingly chaotic phenomena.

Many Mathematicians have endeavored to refer to fractal shapes[4] for over one hundred years, but with the dealing power and imaging aptitudes of modern computers, fractals have relished new popularity because they can be digitally condensed and explored in all of their attractive beauty. Fractals are being used in schools as a visual aid to teaching math, and also in our popular culture as computer-generated surfaces for landscapes and planetary surfaces in the film industry. The use of algorithms to generate fractals can yield complex visual patterns for computer-generated imagery (CGI) applications. Below are some figures.,

A fractal dimension is measured by the ratio organizing out the complexity of a system given its measurement.

A single line has split into three equal segments with the interval $1/3$. MidThe middlemen have been eliminated. In the first iteration, a single edge has separated into two edges. The same process is every edge of the graph. Each edge has been separated into two edges. In the upcoming iteration, the number of edges has increased to twice.

A Koch curve is a fractal curve that can be constructed by taking a single straight line segment and dividing it into three equal parts and replacing it with a pattern of multiple line segments. Then the line segments repeat the same pattern.

Step1:
Draw an equilateral triangle with any measurements.

* It's best if the length of the sides is divisible by 3, because of the nature of this fractal. This will become clear in the next few steps.

Step2:

Divide each side into three equal parts. This is why it is handy to have the sides divisible by three.

Figure-9

Step3:

Draw an equilateral triangle on each middle part. Measure the length of the side, and divided into three equal parts and centre two points draw again new triangle.

Figure-10

Step4:

Divide each outer side into thirds. Now 2nd iteration of triangles covers a bit of the first.

Figure-11

Step5:

Draw an equilateral triangle on each middle part.

*Note how you draw each next iteration of parts that are one 3rd of the last one.

Figure-12

The figure was obtained by trisecting each side of an equilateral triangle and replacing the center segment with two sides of a smaller equilateral triangle projecting outward, then treating the resulting figure the same way, and so on[4]. Like iteration proceeds, the perimeter of the curve increases without limit. The area it encirclesfixes approach ahighercertain, which is $\frac{8}{5}$ the area of the unique triangle.

Above Figure –12, we can color it. How many Colours need for that? According to Chromatic number minimum number of colours, we must use. Need three coloronly.

The concept of "fractal dimension" is attributed to the 20th-century mathematician, [7]Benoit Mandelbrot. His fractal theory was developed in order to try to more quite quantify the

enormous complexity of nature in relatively humble equations. N (the number of miniscule pieces in the final figure) is equal to S (the scaling factor) high to the power D (dimension). It was easy to determine the measurement by merely reading the exponent. This simple concept can be comprehensive to amount to the non-integral dimensions of many fractals. One such fractal is the Van-Koch snowflake that you generated above.

$$N = S^D$$

$$D = \log N / \log S.$$

This is the formula to use for computing the fractal dimension[9] of any *strictly self-similar* fractals. The measurement is a measure of how fully these fractals insert themselves into normal Euclidean space.

Koch Curve

$$N=4, S=3, D=\log 4 / \log 3=1.2618$$

Figure-13

Fractals provide a methodical[10] method to capture the “roughness” of some objects. This method to imprisonment roughness has uses in a wide variety of fields reaching from programming to medicine.

More precise estimate of the fractal dimension[11] of the network topology it, is advisable to use the method of coloring the verified object based on the geometrical structure of such a size and shape as a seed, which permits regulating the range of variation of the area ratio of fractal coating preserve serve self-similarity network.

AREA USED IN FRACTAL GRAPHS:

Most of the significant features of fractal geometry is the fractal dimension. Although many researchers had subsidized to the development and solemnization of fractal dimension (HausdorV 1919, Richardson 1961), it was not up until Mandelbrot (1967) that the fractal dimension concept was firmly established. Mandelbrot argued that if a straight line or a plane is absolute with Euclidean dimension 1 or 2, respectively, then spatial objects such as coastlines that twist in the plane must spontaneously have a fractal measurement between 1 and 2.

GuoqiangShen[12] Given that planar fractal growth can be regarded as a 2-D space-filling process, the planar fractal dimension can positively be used to model 2-D urban growth and urban form. It would be interesting to see a more complete set of fractal dimensions for major urbanized areas in the US or other countries. Such a fractal dimension set may lean more light on

the fascinating nature of fractal dimension as a spatial dimension measure and its role in urban modeling and spatial analysis.

Marc M. Schulze; Natalie Hutchings; Trafford L. Simpson [13] the purpose of this study was to estimate the accurateness of the grading scales by associating the distribution and parting of the orientation images of illustrative redness grading scales to objectives physical attributes of redness distinct by fractal analysis and photometric chromaticity and to use these measures to cross-calibrate the scales. One limitation of the study was that scale reference images were provided at different resolutions (72-300dpi). All image processing techniques, the highest spatial resolution possible is beneficial, particularly when small spatial particulars form the thing of interest.

James R. Riehl and Joao P. Hespanha [14] introduced methods of decomposing three graph optimization problems to achieve upper and lower bounds with much less computation than would be required to solve the complete problems. Additionally, each tricky is formulated in such a way that agrees with multiple levels of hierarchical decomposition. As the number of levels increases, the computation decreases further at the expense of looser bounds on the optimal solution.

Grawiec, Krzysztof Domanska, and Diana [15] presented some drawbacks of these methods and propose fractal local analysis using partitioned iterated function systems with division. Moreover, they introduced a new fractal recognition method based on a dependence graph obtained from the partitioned iterated function system. The planned technique uses a narrow analysis of the shape, which improves the gratitude rate. The efficiency of our method is shown on two test records. The first one was created by the writers. The second one is the MPEG7 CE-Shape-1 PartB record. The gained results show that the planned methodology has led to an important improvement in the recognition rate.

Spencer Hooks [16] fractal-based chromatography applications include: High fructose syrups, Specialty sugars and sweeteners, Biomass hydrolysate, organic acids, Inorganic separations, and Cannabinoid separations.

Many applications of Fractal graphs are available in many fields. In spite of the creative and mathematical value of fractals, their service in computer graphics, computer file compression systems, the architecture of the internet, and medicine is undeniable. So fractals have many uses in technology and the environment. The most significant uses include antennas, signal processing analysis, cell phones, and transistors. Therefore Fractals are hyper-well-organized in their

structure and this allows plants to maximize their exposure to sunlight and also efficiently transport nutrients throughout their cellular structure.

CONCLUSION: The chromatic number of a graph is the minimum number of colors needed to produce a proper coloring of a graph. The formulae of Chromatic numbers are common for iteration of the corresponding graph. It is useful to discover chromatic numbers in a simple way of a very large iteration of a Fractal Graph. We discussed in this paper the Fractal Graph and its uses in various fields. More innovation needs to use Fractal graphs. With fractals still being a comparatively novel topic in mathematics and fresh discoveries being made every year, more fractals' applications are still undiscovered.

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